

EVALUATING PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING ORAL PRESENTATIONS IN PAKISTANI ESL HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Assessment practices play a crucial role in enabling learners to rehearse and prepare for actual evaluations, while constructive feedback supports the development of their speaking proficiency in English. In the context of Pakistani higher education, assessing oral presentations has gained significance with the increasing emphasis on communicative competence. Instructors are expected not only to evaluate learners' performance but also to provide timely feedback that allows students to refine their oral presentation skills. However, this responsibility has created challenges for instructors who must balance pedagogical expectations with institutional deadlines and workload pressures. This study explores the perceptions of Pakistani ESL instructors regarding pedagogical approaches to assessing oral presentations and examines their views on strategies for improving current practices. A qualitative research design was employed using purposive sampling to select instructors from higher education institutions. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, recorded and transcribed, and analysed using thematic analysis. Findings revealed that instructors acknowledged the value of oral presentation assessment in enhancing learners' communication skills, self-confidence, and integration of multiple language skills. Nevertheless, they also highlighted issues related to time constraints, feedback delivery, and resource availability. The study provides practical insights for refining assessment strategies and enhancing the effectiveness of oral presentation courses in Pakistani ESL higher education.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is a fundamental language skill that learners must acquire and master in order to participate effectively in authentic communicative settings (Giang, 2022), such as everyday conversations, academic discussions, and workplace interactions. Within higher education, oral presentations are widely used as an avenue for learners to practise and develop their speaking abilities, as students are often required to present on diverse academic topics. This indicates that tertiary education plays a pivotal role in strengthening learners' oral communication skills (Sahan et al., 2022). In many universities worldwide, including those in Pakistan, oral presentations are increasingly being incorporated into English language and communication courses. Such courses generally cover both theoretical knowledge such as communication models, presentation structures, and rhetorical organization and practical skills, including verbal and non-verbal communication strategies (Zaman, Jawad, & Buriro, 2025). These components help equip learners with the ability to present their ideas effectively and appropriately in academic and professional contexts. Oral communication is also a highly valued competency in the job market (Zaman, Chandio, & Noor, 2025) which further emphasizes the importance of preparing graduates with strong presentation skills.

However, presenting before an audience often poses psychological challenges for students, such as nervousness, anxiety, and intimidation (Smith & Saddano, 2011). In Pakistan, where English is used as a second language and often carries social prestige, these challenges may be magnified due to learners' limited exposure to authentic communicative environments. This makes it imperative for higher education institutions to systematically integrate oral presentation practice into their

curriculum, thereby providing learners with the confidence and competence needed for real-world communication.

Oral presentations, however, are complex tasks that require structured preparation and adherence to certain conventions to be effective (Ahmad Taufik Hidayah & Mohd Nazri, 2019). According to Choo, Yee, and Yeoh (2006), effective presentations must be well-organized, delivered in formal language, and presented through an appropriate method of delivery. Recognizing these demands, universities are increasingly adopting oral presentations as part of their assessment practices (Sahan et al., 2022). Research suggests that such assessments not only improve learners' confidence but also foster creativity, critical thinking, and active participation in classroom learning (Abdelmajdid & Mohd Radzuan, 2019).

Oral presentations can serve both as classroom activities and as assessment tools, depending on the instructional design of the course. They may be used for formative purposes, where instructors provide detailed feedback to guide learners' improvement, or as summative evaluations to measure final performance (Magin & Helmore, 2001). In the Pakistani higher education context, instructors typically follow faculty guidelines in determining the assessment structure, yet their role in delivering constructive and targeted feedback remains essential. Studies emphasize that feedback should address both the content of the presentation (Goodman et al., 2004; Shute, 2008; Govaerts et al., 2013, as cited in Van Ginkel et al., 2017) and the learners' delivery skills (Zainuddin & Che'Lah, 2022). Importantly, instructor feedback is often regarded as more authoritative and credible due to the instructors' expertise and professional standing (Van Ginkel et al., 2017). Once learners receive such feedback, they are more

motivated to enhance their performance in future assessments (Wang et al., 2018; Zainuddin & Che'Lah, 2022). Conversely, a lack of feedback may discourage learners and hinder their willingness to engage in repeated oral presentation practice. In light of these considerations, the present study aims to investigate Pakistani ESL instructors' perceptions regarding the use of oral presentations as an assessment tool in higher education courses, as well as their views on how these assessment practices can be improved.

Statement of the Problem

Oral communication is a vital component of English language proficiency, yet its assessment practices in Pakistani higher education remain underexplored. Existing oral presentation courses often rely on multiple assessments such as informative and persuasive speeches, pitch sessions, and related preparatory activities. While these practices aim to enhance learners' speaking competence, the lack of marks for practice activities and the heavy reliance on instructor feedback place significant workload demands on teachers.

In the context of online and blended learning, instructors face additional challenges, including limited student engagement, increased preparation time, and the burden of providing timely feedback. These challenges may reduce the effectiveness of formative assessments, thereby impacting students' mastery of oral presentation skills.

Given these concerns, there is a pressing need to investigate instructors' perceptions of current oral presentation assessment structures in Pakistani ESL classrooms and explore ways to improve them. Such insights are essential for designing assessment practices that effectively support learners'

communicative competence while remaining sustainable for instructors.

Research Objectives

To explore instructors' perceptions regarding current assessment practices of oral presentation courses in Pakistani ESL higher education.

To identify instructors' perspectives on how oral presentation assessments can be improved to better enhance learners' communicative competence.

Research Questions

What are instructors' perceptions of the current assessment practices for oral presentations in Pakistani ESL classrooms?

How do instructors perceive the improvements needed in oral presentation assessment to strengthen students' oral communication skills?

Significance of the Study

This study holds both theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, it contributes to the limited body of research on oral presentation assessment in Pakistani ESL higher education, offering insights into instructors' perspectives. Practically, the findings can inform curriculum designers, language instructors, and policymakers in developing more effective, student-centered, and sustainable assessment practices. By highlighting the challenges instructors face and suggesting improvements, the study aims to foster better pedagogical approaches that enhance learners' oral proficiency, confidence, and overall academic performance.

Literature Review

Assessment is central to the teaching-learning process as it provides evidence of learners'

mastery of skills, knowledge, and competencies, while also highlighting the challenges they face (Schafer, 1991). Effective assessment practices not only evaluate student performance but also guide improvement by identifying weaknesses and offering constructive feedback (Yan & Cheng, 2015). Research has emphasized that assessment practices strongly influence learners' learning experiences and outcomes (Kitula et al., 2018; To & Carless, 2016). When carried out effectively, assessments can enhance confidence, skill development, and motivation. Conversely, poorly structured assessments may hinder learning and lead to unsatisfactory performance (Ibarra-Sáiz & Rodríguez-Gómez, 2015).

The role of instructors in assessment is crucial. Xu and Brown (2016) argue that instructors must be equipped with appropriate knowledge, techniques, and evaluative skills to ensure fairness and effectiveness. Studies have highlighted inconsistencies in instructors' assessment practices, often linked to differences in experience, training, and institutional support (Postareff et al., 2007; Alkharusi, 2008). Such inconsistencies may result in bias, unfair grading, and misalignment with students' actual performance (Brown & Remesal, 2012). Sambell (2016) stresses the need for relevant and reliable assessment methods to align with course learning outcomes.

Institutional structures also shape assessment practices. In many contexts, universities predetermine the type, weightage, and format of assessments, limiting instructors' autonomy (Lyamtane & Ogoti, 2018). While this ensures uniformity, it may restrict innovation in assessment methods. Moreover, lack of training opportunities further exacerbates the gap between institutional expectations and instructors' practical skills (Cheema et al., 2022). This suggests the

importance of continuous professional development for instructors, particularly when syllabi are revised.

The COVID-19 pandemic added further complexity by shifting assessments to online platforms, requiring instructors to adapt to new modes of delivery and feedback (Panadero et al., 2022). While this transition fostered flexibility, it also increased workload, reduced learner engagement, and posed challenges such as unreliable internet connectivity and doubts about students' comprehension (Gula, 2022). These issues became particularly evident in teaching oral presentation skills, where instructors struggled with limited student proficiency, inadequate vocabulary, pronunciation errors, and learners' fear of making mistakes (Iqbal et al., 2019).

In the Pakistani ESL context, these challenges are even more pronounced due to large class sizes, exam-oriented learning, and limited exposure to English outside classrooms. Learners often lack confidence and communicative competence, which hinders their ability to perform effectively in oral presentations. At the same time, instructors face pressure to balance assessment workloads with providing meaningful feedback.

Therefore, there is a need to examine instructors' perceptions of oral presentation assessment practices in Pakistani higher education. Understanding their experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement can contribute to more effective, context-sensitive assessment approaches that foster learners' oral communication skills while reducing instructors' stress.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a **qualitative research design** to explore instructors' perceptions of assessment practices for oral presentations in

Pakistani higher education. A **semi-structured interview** approach was employed, allowing flexibility for instructors to share in-depth experiences while ensuring coverage of key themes (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Bryman, 2016). This design was deemed suitable as it provides nuanced insights into challenges, perceptions, and suggestions for improving oral presentation assessment in ESL classrooms.

Sampling

A **purposive sampling strategy** was used to select participants with relevant experience in teaching and assessing oral presentations (Gill, 2020). Six instructors from public and private universities in Karachi participated. They represented varying levels of teaching and assessment experience: two with less than 5 years, two with 5–10 years, and two with over 10 years. To maintain confidentiality, participants were identified as P1–P6.

Data Collection

Prior to data collection, **ethical clearance** was obtained from the university research committee. Participants were briefed about the study's purpose, provided informed consent, and assured of anonymity and voluntary participation. Data were collected through **online video interviews** due to accessibility and scheduling constraints. Each interview was audio–video recorded with consent to ensure accuracy and reliability of data.

Data Analysis

The data were transcribed and analysed using **thematic analysis**, which allowed identification of recurring themes and patterns in instructors' perceptions (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Coding was carried out manually, followed by categorisation into themes reflecting challenges, assessment practices,

and recommendations for improvement in oral presentation assessment.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings in response to the first research question: What are the perceptions of instructors on the assessment practices of the English for Oral Presentation course? The focus here is on the sufficiency of oral practices assigned to learners.

Theme one: Sufficiency of Oral Practices

The instructors were asked whether the requirement of submitting ten weekly video-recorded activities was sufficient for students to develop their oral presentation skills.

Instructor L2 emphasized the benefits of sustained practice, stating that “the ten activities should be able to help them to get used to speaking, get used to communicating... I think it's a good practice.” Similarly, L3 acknowledged the sufficiency of the activities but remained cautious about students' perspectives: “Yes, I think they're okay, sufficient, because you know, we need to at least have like three or four weeks of classes... So, I think it's sufficient. But I'm not sure about the perception of students... They will have a different idea.”

L5 also agreed on the adequacy of the ten activities but highlighted the importance of learner engagement: “Sufficient, yes. To prepare, yes. Assuming that they are making use of the activities, which I think is the concern... If the group itself is active and they care about the subject enough to really take the activity seriously, then they can definitely benefit.”

From these views, it is evident that several instructors (L2, L3, L5) believed that the weekly activities were sufficient for students to rehearse and prepare for graded assessments. Their responses suggest that

consistent practice, coupled with peer and instructor feedback, has the potential to enhance learners' communicative competence, provided that learners take the tasks seriously. This reflects findings by Schafer (1991) and Yan & Cheng (2015), who argued that assessment practices encourage learners to identify weaknesses and improve performance when taken meaningfully.

In contrast, other instructors considered the requirement excessive. L4 reported: "The ten practices, yes, it's definitely more than enough for them. In fact, some of my students... didn't even submit some of the practices. I believe it's because they felt overwhelmed." Similarly, L6 felt that the workload was too heavy, observing that "ten activities were quite many for them... I would say giving two activities would be ample enough for each assessment because towards the end of the semester the few students actually did not submit the activities."

These opposing perspectives indicate a divergence in how instructors perceive student capacity for sustained oral practice. While some view ten activities as an adequate scaffold for skill-building, others believe such requirements risk overwhelming learners and leading to disengagement. The variation may be attributed to differences in class sizes, learner proficiency levels, and institutional expectations across universities.

In the Pakistani ESL context, this finding is particularly relevant, as many learners struggle with limited exposure to English outside the classroom and often face anxiety in oral communication tasks (Iqbal et al., 2019). Thus, while regular practice is essential, the volume and intensity of assigned activities must balance skill development with learners' capacity to cope with academic demands. As Chris (2016) suggests, effective oral presentation practice requires not only frequent rehearsal but also a non-threatening

learning environment where students feel motivated rather than pressured.

Theme two: Applicable Knowledge

Instructors were also asked whether the skills and concepts taught in class were practically applied by students during their oral presentations.

Instructor P4 highlighted that most learners were able to transfer classroom knowledge into practice. She observed that "students incorporated key elements of effective speech-making such as structuring the introduction, body, and conclusion, employing paraphrasing strategies, and using transitional signals appropriately. Learners followed the taught organizational framework, including the sequencing of content, which enhanced their ability to communicate ideas in a logical manner."

Instructor P6 similarly noted that "learners demonstrated an understanding of essential presentation components such as attention-getters, establishing speaker credibility, and articulating a central idea. While students effectively applied these strategies in informative presentations, they struggled with more advanced structures, such as Monroe's Motivated Sequence in persuasive speeches. Nevertheless, they were attempting to apply theoretical concepts in practice, reflecting a degree of internalization of classroom learning."

The findings indicate that Pakistani ESL learners generally apply classroom-taught strategies in their oral presentations, though the extent of application varies across genres of speech. The excerpts suggest that structured teaching, coupled with interactive classroom practices such as question-answer sessions and teacher feedback, may enhance learners' ability to implement knowledge effectively. This aligns with Tsang (2020), who argued that interactive pedagogical

practices provide learners with clearer goals and direction in their learning process.

Theme Three: Presentation Skills Improvement

Participants were asked whether learners improved their presentation skills after completing their oral presentation practices.

Instructor P3 emphasized the importance of syllabus alignment with essential presentation requirements, noting that “students need to understand the intricacies of presentation skills, such as knowing the audience, curating content according to their level of understanding, and presenting ideas effectively. These aspects, if emphasized in the syllabus, directly contribute to students’ improvement.”

On the other hand, Instructor P5 raised concerns about the limitations of online delivery, explaining that “most students tend to rely heavily on scripts or detailed bullet points during online presentations. They lack spontaneity and rehearsal, unlike in face-to-face classes where we could encourage more natural delivery. This remains a major constraint in skill development.”

The role of feedback emerged as a central theme. Instructor P4 stated that “intervention sessions where I highlight missing components, such as essential items in the introduction or transitions, help students refine their presentations.” Similarly, Instructor P2 observed that “some students who take feedback seriously show visible improvement,” while Instructor P1 added that “students often confuse persuasive and informative speeches, particularly in their use of vocabulary, and need consistent feedback to avoid such errors.”

Feedback, therefore, was seen as a crucial pedagogical tool to enhance learners’ oral presentation skills, resonating with the findings of Zulhermindra and Hadiarni

(2020), who noted that instructor feedback, especially through videotaped reviews, significantly improved learners’ skills and self-monitoring abilities.

In addition, instructors acknowledged the role of confidence-building through repeated practice. Instructor P3 reflected that “students show visible improvement in confidence when presenting repeatedly in front of the camera,” while Instructor P6 affirmed that “classroom activities play an important role in this improvement.” However, Instructor P4 noted variations, explaining that “some students make remarkable progress, while others show little to no improvement despite multiple activities.”

Overall, the findings suggest that Pakistani ESL learners can improve their oral presentation skills when provided with structured practice opportunities, constructive feedback, and supportive environments. This aligns with prior studies (Mahdi, 2022; Ahmad et al., 2022; Chris, 2016), which demonstrate that sustained oral practice, combined with feedback and confidence-building strategies, enhances both communicative competence and self-efficacy.

Theme Four: Other Integrated Skills

Since oral presentations are not confined to speaking alone, instructors were also asked whether students benefitted from other integrated skills during the course.

Instructor P2 pointed out that “digital skills are also involved, because even though students are not allowed to edit extensively, they still design their PowerPoint slides. That in itself is a useful skill. Beyond that, the submission of videos and Wiki feedback contributes to communication skills, since these processes create two-way interactions. Indirectly, students also develop professionalism and leadership qualities, especially group leaders who learn how to

interact, delegate, and coordinate with team members.”

Similarly, Instructor P4 emphasized the importance of research and digital literacy: “I would say some students did apply these skills. For instance, they referred to friends for guidance, searched for materials, and improved their digital literacy when I instructed them to use the PTAR online library for journals. They also practiced paraphrasing, and I shared resources such as websites and YouTube speech samples to help them familiarize themselves with authentic content.”

From these responses, it can be inferred that oral presentation practices facilitated the development of complementary skills beyond speaking. Both instructors agreed that learners’ digital skills improved, particularly in creating slides, navigating online resources, and engaging with digital platforms for feedback and collaboration. Furthermore, research skills such as paraphrasing, evaluating sources, and organizing content were strengthened through the repeated preparation process.

Equally important, soft skills such as teamwork, leadership, and communication were embedded in the process of preparing and presenting. Learners were required to collaborate, distribute responsibilities, and support one another, which fostered a sense of professionalism.

These findings suggest that oral presentation practices serve as a multimodal learning experience in ESL classrooms, preparing learners for both academic and professional communication. In the Pakistani context, where digital literacy and teamwork are increasingly emphasized in higher education, these integrated skills are crucial. As Shala and Shatri (2022) note, when learners acquire practical skills that go beyond language itself, they perceive the learning process as more

engaging and meaningful, which in turn enhances their motivation and performance.

Theme Five: Suggestions for Improvement

The second research objective aimed to identify possible improvements in the English for Oral Presentation course. Instructors were asked to share their perceptions and recommendations for enhancing course effectiveness.

Instructor L3 suggested integrating technology and social media into the assessment process: “Yes, the RP and the team members should make improvements. For example, and this was suggested by my colleague, she basically suggested the use of social media applications such as TikTok or Instagram.” This reflects a growing recognition of digital platforms as engaging tools for oral practice, especially for Generation Z learners who are already active on such platforms. The integration of social media could enhance student motivation and provide authentic, audience-driven contexts for presentations.

Instructor L5 emphasized the importance of collaboration in preparing learners for professional contexts: “Pair work or group work? The thing about the workplace is that when they enter later, they will be working in teams. They will not be producing slides alone. They will be producing it with different departments, with different people.” This underscores the relevance of embedding teamwork within assessment practices, as collaborative learning mirrors the communication and project-based skills required in real workplace environments.

On the other hand, **Instructor L6** and **Instructor L4** expressed concerns about the workload and suggested reducing the number of practice activities. L6 noted: “Cut down the number of activities...” while L4 elaborated:

“Okay. Personally speaking, I would say that the ten activities still is a lot. The reason being I don't know if it is because of me or what, because I'm kind of a particular person. So whenever I provide feedback, it's very in detail. So it takes a lot of time... so I feel that the practices are kind of like ten is still a little bit too much.” Their perspectives indicate that the current workload may not only overwhelm students but also create challenges for instructors in providing timely, quality feedback.

Taken together, these suggestions highlight three main areas of improvement:

Integration of Technology and Social Media: Leveraging platforms like TikTok or Instagram could make assessments more engaging, accessible, and aligned with learners' digital habits.

Collaborative Learning Approaches: Embedding group or pair work could enhance teamwork, peer feedback, and problem-solving, while also reflecting professional realities.

Curriculum Load Adjustment: Reducing the number of practice activities may improve quality over quantity, ensuring that both learners and instructors can focus more on meaningful feedback and skill development. In the Pakistani ESL context, these recommendations are particularly relevant. Digital integration aligns with the Higher Education Commission's (HEC) ongoing push for blended and technology-enhanced learning. Group-based assessments resonate with collectivist cultural learning tendencies where collaboration is valued. Finally, revising activity requirements can help balance workload, especially in institutions where large class sizes and limited resources

often hinder effective individualized feedback.

As Law (2022) argued, curriculum review is an essential process in adapting to the changing educational landscape. However, such revisions must carefully consider the impact on all stakeholders—faculty, instructors, and learners—ensuring that changes enhance both learning outcomes and teaching feasibility.

Conclusion

Despite numerous pedagogical approaches proposed to enhance learners' oral presentation skills, mastering this competency continues to present challenges. This study explored Pakistani ESL instructors' perceptions of assessment practices in oral presentation courses and their views on potential improvements.

Findings indicate that instructors generally perceived the current assessment practices positively, considering them sufficient for preparing learners to improve their oral presentation skills—particularly when learners engaged seriously with the weekly activities and received constructive feedback. Instructors highlighted that students were able to apply classroom knowledge, such as paraphrasing strategies, transitional markers, and attention-getters, in their presentations. These skills were not only transferable to other academic courses requiring oral tasks but also contributed to learners' long-term communicative competence.

The instructors further noted that regular practice and feedback enhanced learners' confidence, presentation delivery, and other integrated skills, including digital literacy, research, and teamwork. Thus, the oral presentation course was considered relevant both for academic purposes and for professional communication in future workplace contexts.

However, several areas for improvement were identified. Suggestions included integrating technology and social media platforms (e.g., TikTok, YouTube) for assessment submission, adopting collaborative tasks such as pair or group work to reflect workplace practices, and reducing the number of weekly practice activities to avoid overwhelming both students and instructors.

Overall, the study concludes that the oral presentation course holds significant potential in equipping learners with essential academic and professional communication skills, though curriculum adjustments are needed to increase its efficiency and sustainability. Future research should expand beyond a single institution and incorporate perspectives from students and administrators, potentially employing quantitative or mixed-methods designs to generate broader insights into effective oral presentation assessment practices in Pakistani universities.

References

- Abdelmajdid, B., & Mohd Radzuan, N. R. (2019). Engineering lecturer's perceptions of student self-assessment in enhancing technical oral presentation skills. *Global Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 9(4), 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.18844/gjflt.v9i4.4324>
- Alkharusi, H. (2008). Effects of classroom assessment practices on students' achievement goals. *Educational Assessment*, 13(4), 243–266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10627190802602509>
- Ahmad, S. N., Rahmat, N. H., Shahabani, N. S., & Khairuddin, Z. (2022). Discovering the relationship between communication strategies and fear of oral presentation among university students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(9), 1185–1212. https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/14859/discovering-the-relationship-between-communication-strategies-and-fear-of-oral-presentation-among-university-students.pdf
- Arwae, S., & Soontornwipast, K. (2022). Developing scientific oral presentation competence focusing on question-and-answer sessions of high-ability science students in Thailand. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 15(2), 377–411. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1358705.pdf>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brown, G. T., & Remesal, A. (2012). Prospective teachers' conceptions of assessment: A cross-cultural comparison. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 15(1), 75–89. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_sjop.2012.v15.n1.37286
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods* (5th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Cheema, S., Siddiqui, M., & Massod, S. (2022). Perceptions of teachers about assessment practices at primary level in private schools of Lahore. *Global Educational Studies Review*, 7(2), 263–274. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022\(VII-II\).25](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2022(VII-II).25)
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Cuic Tankovic, A., Kapeš, J., & Benazić, D. (2023). Measuring the importance of communication skills in tourism. *Economic Research-Ekonomska*

- Istraživanja, 36(1), 460–479.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2022.2077790>
- Gill, S. L. (2020). Qualitative sampling methods. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 36(4), 579–581.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0890334420949218>
- Gula, L. P. (2022). Challenges encountered by the teachers handling oral speech communication courses in the era of COVID-19 pandemic. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 234–244.
<https://philarchive.org/archive/GULCEB>
- Iqbal, Z., Alvi, E., & Shafi, F. (2019). Prospective teachers' perceptions of oral presentations: An exploration of challenges involved. *Pakistan Journal of Education*, 36(2), 137–163.
<http://journal.aiou.edu.pk/pjeojs/index.php/PJE/article/view/509/pdf>
- Kitula, P. R., Kireti, P., & Wambiya, P. (2018). Perceived efficacy of university lecturers in conducting assessment among selected universities in Tanzania. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(6), 121–130.
<https://www.ijern.com/journal/2018/June-2018/09.pdf>
- Law, M. Y. (2022). A Review of curriculum change and innovation for higher education. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 10(2), 16–23.
<https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v10i2.5448>
- Lyamtane, R. E., & Ogoti, E. (2018). Participation of students in university governance: A case of Mwenge Catholic University, Tanzania. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(3).
<https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v6i3.e107>
- Magin, D., & Helmore, P. (2001). Peer and teacher assessments of oral presentation skills: How reliable are they? *Studies in Higher Education*, 26(3), 287–298.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070120076264>
- Mahdi, D. A. (2022). Improving speaking and presentation skills through interactive multimedia environment for non-native speakers of English. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 21582440221079811.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221079811>
- Matovu, M., & Madziah Zubairi, A. (2014). Self-perceived assessment competencies and practices among university lecturers. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 6(2), 269–284.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-04-2013-0020>
- Murillo-Zamorano, L. R., & Montanero, M. (2017). Oral presentations in higher education: A comparison of the impact of peer and teacher feedback. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 43(1), 138–150.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2017.1303032>
- Nik Ismail Azlan, N. M., Yusuf, N. K., Panah, E., Soopar, A. A., & Norazizan, M. H. (2022). English language needs among services sector employees in Malaysia's new norm. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(9), 1213–1225.
https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/14655/english-language-needs-among-services-sector-employees-in-malaysias-new-norm.pdf
- Postareff, L., Lindblom-Ylänne, S., & Nevgi, A. (2007). The effect of pedagogical training on teaching in higher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23(5), 557–571. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-0079087-z>
- Sahan, A., Abi, B. K., Wisrance, M. W., & Seran, Y. (2022). Exploring oral

- presentation performance: Level of mastery and common problems of EFL students from selected university. *REiLA: Journal of Research and Innovation in Language*, 4(3), 335–343. <https://doi.org/10.31849/reila.11005>
- Sambell, K. (2016). Assessment and feedback in higher education: Considerable room for improvement? *Student Engagement in Higher Education*, 1(1). <https://193.60.48.124/index.php/raise/article/view/392/350>
- Schafer, W. D. (1991). Essential assessment skills in professional education of teachers. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 10(1), 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.1991.tb00170.x>
- Shala, L., & Shatri, K. (2022). Evaluating the effect of interactive digital presentations on students' performance during technology class. *Education Research International*, 2022, 3337313. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3337313>
- Smith, C. M., & Sodano, T. M. (2011). Integrating lecture capture as a teaching strategy to improve student presentation skills through self-assessment. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 12(3), 151–162. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787411415082>
- Taufiq-Hail, G. A. M., Aljahromi, D., Sarea, A., & Kostikova, I. (2021, November) Academic staff perceptions on students' traditional assessment transformations towards online evaluation during COVID-19 pandemic in higher education: A preliminary study from two diverse cultures. In *2021 Sustainable Leadership and Academic Excellence International Conference (SLAE)* (pp. 16–25). IEEE <https://doi.org/10.1109/SLAE54202.2021.9686904>
- Ting, S. H., Marzuki, E., Chuah, K. M., Misieng, J., & Jerome, C. (2017). Employers' views on the importance of English proficiency and communication skill for employability in Malaysia. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 7(2), 315–327. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v7i2.8132>
- To, J., & Carless, D. (2016). Making productive use of exemplars: Peer discussion and teacher guidance for positive transfer of strategies. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 40(6), 746–764. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2015.1014317>
- Tsang, A. (2020). Enhancing learners' awareness of oral presentation (delivery) skills in the context of self-regulated learning. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 21(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787417731214>
- Van Ginkel, S., Gulikers, J., Biemans, H., & Mulder, M. (2017). Fostering oral presentation performance: Does the quality of feedback differ when provided by the teacher, peers or peers guided by tutor? *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 42(6), 953–966. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2016.1212984>
- Zaman, M., Jawad, M., & Buriro, G. S. (2025). Understanding ESL lecturers' beliefs and teaching methodologies in the context of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in Karachi. *ACADEMIA International Journal for Social Sciences*, 4(1), 447 <https://doi.org/10.63056/ACAD.004.01.0057>
- Zaman, M., Chandio, A. A., & Noor, H. (2025) Evaluating the influence of Meta-AI on enhancing English reading

comprehension proficiency: An
experimental study within a social media
application framework Social Science
Review Archives, 3(1), 2223–
2233<https://doi.org/10.70670/sra.v3i1.533>